

Teaching Software Engineering Experimentation: a Survey

The survey was built by [ANONYMIZED]

This survey aims at identifying actual practices and instruments used to teach Software Engineering Experimentation to undergraduate and graduate students.

The estimated time to complete the questionnaire is less than 10 minutes.

STATEMENT OF INFORMED CONSENT

By answering this survey, you agree to permit the researcher to use and disclose the anonymous information provided as described below.

CONDITIONS AND STIPULATIONS

1. I understand that all information is confidential. I will not be personally identified. I agree to complete the survey for research purposes and that the data derived from this anonymous survey may be published in journals, conferences, and blog posts
2. I understand that my participation in this research survey is totally voluntary and that declining to participate involves no penalty or loss of benefits. I may withdraw my participation at any time. I also understand that I may decline to answer any question that I am not comfortable answering.
3. I understand that I can contact the researcher if I have any questions about the research survey. I am aware that my consent will not directly benefit me. I am also aware that the author will maintain the data collected in perpetuity and may utilize data for future academic work.
4. By clicking the button below I freely provide consent and acknowledge my rights as a voluntary research participant as outlined above and provide consent to the researchers to use my information in conducting research. I also confirm that I am of legal age to fill in this survey.

Demographics

Name

E-mail (for follow up contact)

Institution

Country *

Software Engineering Experimentation

What sector is the educational institution where you teach the concepts of Software Engineering Experimentation? *

- Public
- Private
- Funded by private and public resources

At what level(s) of education you teach Software Engineering Experimentation? *

- Undergraduate course(s)
- Master's
- Ph.D.
- Specialization courses, such as MBAs

How long (in years) have you been teaching Software Engineering Experimentation? *

The materials you use to teach the concepts of Software Engineering Experimentation are: *

- Your own prepared materials
- Third-party materials
- Both

Do you provide students any study guides to, for instance, keeping track of tasks and deadlines on Software Engineering Experimentation? If Yes, please describe how you make the information available. *

How are Software Engineering Experimentation concepts taught? *

- In a course dedicated exclusively to Software Engineering Experimentation
- Spread out in one or more courses as a means to evaluate theory and technology
- Both cases

How do you make the materials available to your students? *

- By email
- Dropbox
- Github
- Personal or Institution's Website
- Moodle
- Other: _____

Do the materials used or produced by you follow any open licenses, for example, Creative Commons? *

- Yes
- No
- Some of them

What basic/reference bibliography (books, articles, etc) of Software Engineering Experimentation you adopt? Please list them or inform DOI or URL when available.

What is the evaluation method used to measure whether the objectives of the course have been achieved?

- Articles
- Seminars
- Written Essays
- Technical Reports
- Practical Projects
- Other:

What materials do you use for teaching Software Engineering Experimentation concepts? For example, slides, articles, class notes. *

We are analyzing the Software Engineering Experimentation state of the practice. In case your materials could be shared, would you mind provide an URL to them in the next field?

URL to materials:

Could you provide us your Software Engineering Experimentation course's syllabus? A syllabus is a student-driven guide to a course and what will be expected from students in the course. *Generally it will include course policies, rules and regulations, required texts, a list of topics, and a schedule of assignments. A syllabus can tell students nearly everything they need to know about how a course will be run and what will be expected of them. (adapted from Stanford Univ.)*

What learning practices do you adopt to teach Software Engineering Experimentation? *

What best practices worked and did not work on teaching Software Engineering Experimentation? *

Please, use this field to provide any feedback, suggestion or comment on this survey.
